

Influence of Soil Properties on Interactions of Pesticides with Soils

A. K. MANDAL^a and M. ADHIKARI^{*b}

^aDivision of Soils and Crop Management, Central Soil Salinity Research Institute, Karnal-132 001

^bAE-829, Salt Lake City, Calcutta-700 064

Manuscript received 10 November 1994, revised 12 July 1995, accepted 30 August 1995

Freundlich equation has been used to characterise the adsorption of metacid (methyl parathion) and sumithion (fenitrothion) on soils (untreated) and soils free of organic matter (O.M.) and sesquioxides. Stepwise multiple regression analysis shows that organic matter and Fe₂O₃ content of untreated soils largely (99.9%) control adsorption (*K* value) of metacid while the organic matter, Al₂O₃ and clay content account mainly (99.4%) adsorption (*K* value) of sumithion. Among the other soil properties, specific surface area is found to contribute significantly in variation of adsorption of metacid and sumithion by untreated and treated soils. The adsorption of pesticides is temperature-dependent and exothermic in nature. Evaluation of thermodynamic parameters indicates the physical nature of adsorption. The irreversible nature of adsorption is revealed from desorption study and shows hysteresis. Percent desorption values indicate an inverse relation with organic matter content of the soils (untreated).

The nature and extent of sorption depend upon the nature of the soil constituents, pesticides and other environmental factors, like temperature, soil reaction, soil moisture¹⁻⁵. Soil constituents with their high specific surface areas may influence adsorption which inhibit translocation, volatility and leachability thereby affecting the persistence of these pesticides³⁻⁷. The organic colloidal fraction of soil is an active component affecting retention of pesticides in soil, yet it cannot be the sole factor for the higher adsorption capacity of soils^{8,9}. Besides organics, other inorganic soil constituents may also play a role in adsorption⁷⁻⁹. Previous studies^{8,9} on adsorption of metacid (*O,O*-dimethyl-*O-p*-nitrophenol phosphorothioate, water solubility 56 mg dm⁻³ at 25°) and sumithion (*O,O*-dimethyl-*O-4-nitro-3-methylphenylthiophosphate*, water solubility 30 mg dm⁻³ at 25°) emphasised the nature of retention by soils and soil components. The present approach is to investigate comparative adsorption behaviour of metacid and sumithion on soil surface and to evaluate the role of soil constituents on such adsorption.

Results and Discussion

The physicochemical characteristics of the soils are given in Table 1.

The adsorption of metacid and sumithion by untreated, organic matter-free (O.M.-free) and oxide-free (OX-free) soils was found to be best fitted with the Freundlich equation (eqn. 1) within the experimental range of concentration used,

$$x/m = KC^{1/n} \quad (1)$$

The isotherms (Figs. 1 and 2) for adsorption of metacid and sumithion are close to L- and S-types¹⁰. The S-type isotherms were observed for adsorption of sumithion. In case of adsorption of metacid S-type isotherms were found in Mohitnagar, Kakdwip and Krishnagar soils having high to moderately high organic matter content (3.19, 1.53 and 1.07%). The L-type isotherms are noted in the Burdwan and Purulia soils with comparatively lower organic matter content. Similar observations were reported by earlier workers^{3,4,7}.

The values of *K* and 1/*n* are presented in Table 2 for different adsorbate-adsorbent interactions at different temperatures. The higher adsorption by Mohitnagar soil (untreated) is due to its higher organic matter content while the high clay content of Kakdwip soil (O.M.-free/OX-free) is responsible for its high retention capacity of pesticides^{7,11}. The *K* values are higher for metacid than for sumithion for all the adsorbent-adsorbate interactions. It

TABLE 1—PHYSICO-CHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF UNTREATED AND TREATED SOILS

Soil	Organic matter %	Mechanical comp. (%)			Free oxides (%)		EC _e dS m ⁻¹	pH(1 : 2.5)			Cation-exch. cap. (cmol (p ⁺)kg ⁻¹)			Specific surface area m ² g ⁻¹		
		Sand	Silt	Clay	Fe ₂ O ₃	Al ₂ O ₃		Un-tre-ated	O.M.-free*	OX-Free*	Un-tre-ated	O.M.-free*	OX-Free*	Un-tre-ated	O.M.-free*	OX-Free*
Burdwan	0.65	63.73	22.46	13.16	0.28	0.81	0.17	5.8	4.3	9.4	15.1	10.0	27.5	77	163	25
Kakdwip	1.52	4.13	36.57	57.74	0.19	3.90	1.74	6.6	5.4	8.2	21.4	22.5	30.5	135	103	35
Krishnagar	1.07	61.03	12.47	26.50	0.07	1.53	0.34	6.5	4.8	9.0	18.5	18.2	28.5	109	77	29
Mohitnagar	3.19	49.90	25.50	24.60	0.03	1.04	0.19	5.1	5.2	8.1	16.2	14.3	27.7	10.3	64	26
Purulia	0.89	79.36	11.50	8.22	0.20	0.09	0.06	5.6	8.4	8.8	13.6	5.0	24.3	70	38	19

*O.M.-Free = organic matter - free soils; OX-Free = Oxide free - soils.

TABLE 2—FREUNDLICH CONSTANT (*K* AND *1/n*) FOR ADSORPTION OF METACID AND SUMITHION BY UNTREATED AND TREATED SOILS AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Soil	Treatment	<i>K</i> ($\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$)						<i>1/n</i>					
		Metacid			Sumithion			Metacid			Sumithion		
		33°	24°	10°	33°	24°	10°	33°	24°	10°	33°	24°	10°
Burdwan	Untreated	7.94	10.00	20.00	5.00	7.00	14.10	0.65	0.60	0.55	0.64	0.62	0.58
	O.M.-free	6.30	7.94	8.90	4.46	6.30	8.91	0.51	0.54	0.56	0.78	0.71	0.65
	OX-free	4.46	7.07	7.94	3.98	5.62	7.07	0.56	0.54	0.54	0.80	0.71	0.77
Kakdwip	Untreated	14.12	31.60	56.20	11.20	15.80	19.90	0.51	0.39	0.28	0.60	0.57	0.56
	O.M.-free	12.58	14.12	19.95	8.91	10.00	15.84	0.44	0.43	0.42	0.62	0.60	0.57
	OX-free	11.22	12.58	17.78	7.07	8.91	12.58	0.42	0.45	0.39	0.68	0.64	0.63
Krishnagar	Untreated	10.00	28.10	44.60	7.00	10.00	17.70	0.49	0.42	0.38	0.59	0.56	0.55
	O.M.-free	8.90	11.22	17.78	6.30	8.91	12.58	0.48	0.47	0.41	0.68	0.63	0.62
	OX-free	6.30	10.00	15.84	5.62	7.07	11.22	0.43	0.46	0.47	0.62	0.59	0.58
Mohitnagar	Untreated	25.10	39.80	79.40	12.50	17.70	44.60	0.38	0.32	0.25	0.51	0.50	0.50
	O.M.-free	7.94	10.00	15.84	5.62	7.07	10.00	0.50	0.47	0.43	0.50	0.50	0.53
	OX-free	5.62	8.91	14.12	5.01	6.30	7.94	0.56	0.50	0.46	0.65	0.70	0.70
Purulia	Untreated	8.90	25.10	31.60	5.60	8.90	15.80	6.56	0.52	0.50	0.64	0.69	0.70
	O.M.-free	5.01	7.07	8.91	4.46	5.62	7.94	0.58	0.54	0.52	0.55	0.51	0.50
	OX-free	3.98	7.07	14.12	3.54	5.01	7.07	0.57	0.51	0.42	0.87	0.78	0.76

Fig. 1. Isotherms for adsorption of metacid by Burdwan soil at different temperatures: (○) 33°, (●) 24° and (Δ) 10°.

Fig. 2. Isotherms for adsorption of sumithion by Kakdwip soil at 24°. (○) untreated, (●) O. M.-free and (Δ) OX-free soil.

arises possible due to the presence of a CH₃ group instead of H in sumithion which causes steric effect resulting in lower adsorption (*K* values). Similar results were reported¹² for sorption of organophosphorus pesticides in relation to their structure by soils with a broad range of clay and organic matter contents. The untreated soils show higher retention (*K* values) than organic matter-free soils. The adsorption of pesticides in organic matter-free soils is more than that in oxide-free soils. The interaction of polar functional groups (P-O, P=S, NO₂) as well as conjugated ring structure of metacid and sumithion with polar functional groups of organic matter in untreated soil and charged clay surfaces of treated soils (O.M.-free and OX-free) favour higher adsorption^{5,12-14}.

Stepwise regression analysis¹⁵ was attempted to find the relative contributions of soil components on pesticide adsorption,

$$K_1 = 0.777 + 7.854 \text{ O.M.} + 10.623 \text{ Fe}_2\text{O}_3 \quad (R^2 = 0.999^{**}) \quad (2)$$

(metacid) (0.205)** (1.972)*

$$K_1 = 0.195 + 1.699 \text{ O.M.} - 5.682 \text{ Al}_2\text{O}_3 + 0.535 \text{ Cl} \quad (R^2 = 0.994^{**}) \quad (3)$$

(sumithion) (1.294) (2.222) (0.615)

It is observed from the above relations that organic matter plays a major role in the retention of metacid and sumithion. Similar results were reported by several authors^{5-7,12,13}. The same technique when applied separately between *K* (at 33°) and pH, CEC and specific surface area of the untreated soil, shows that the contribution of specific surface area (SSA) is much higher in comparison to cation exchange capacity,

$$K_1 = 0.544 + 0.351 \text{ SSA} - 1.300 \text{ CEC} \quad (R^2 = 0.858) \quad (4)$$

(0.445) (2.633)

$$K_2 = 0.171 + 0.210 \text{ SSA} - 0.746 \text{ CEC} \quad (R^2 = 0.959^*) \quad (5)$$

(0.142) (0.844)

In case of organic matter-free soils, clay content accounts for the major variations of adsorption followed by Al₂O₃ and Fe₂O₃,

$$K_1 = 0.310 + 0.562 \text{ Cl} - 5.162 \text{ Al}_2\text{O}_3 + 5.141 \text{ Fe}_2\text{O}_3 \quad (R^2 = 0.977^*) \quad (6)$$

(0.300) (3.987) (7.285)

$$K_2 = 0.230 + 0.437 \text{ Cl} - 4.302 \text{ Al}_2\text{O}_3 + 4.395 \text{ Fe}_2\text{O}_3 \quad (R^2 = 0.977^*) \quad (7)$$

(0.187) (2.916) (5.328)

Similarly, specific surface area has an important contribution on the adsorption of metacid and sumithion by O.M.-free soils,

$$K_1 = 0.039 + 0.097 \text{ SSA} + 0.097 \text{ CEC} \quad (R^2 = 0.0995^{**}) \quad (8)$$

(0.039) (0.184)

$$K_2 = -0.062 + 0.067 \text{ SSA} + 0.215 \text{ pH} + 0.011 \text{ CES} \quad (R^2 = 0.995^{**}) \quad (9)$$

(0.016) (0.166) (0.028)

The adsorption of metacid and sumithion is controlled by clay content of oxide-free soils,

$$K_1 = 0.744 + 0.214 \text{ Cl} \quad (R^2 = 0.959) \quad (10)$$

(0.025^{**})

$$K_2 = 0.979 + 0.156 \text{ Cl} \quad (R^2 = 0.880) \quad (11)$$

(0.033)^*

Besides, significant contributions of specific surface area on adsorption of metacid and sumithion are found,

$$K_1 = -0.647 + 0.444 \text{ SSA} - 0.645 \text{ pH} \quad (R^2 = 0.983^*) \quad (12)$$

(0.103^*) (0.324)

$$K_2 = 0.008 + 0.233 \text{ SSA} - 0.141 \text{ pH} \quad (R^2 = 0.996^{**}) \quad (13)$$

(0.034^*) (0.107)

It is observed from the above relations that the contribution of organic fraction of untreated soils is much higher in comparison to the inorganic fractions. Organic matter re-

tains more metacid than sumithion. The pesticides molecules show higher affinities towards clay surface rather than oxides after removing organic matter from the untreated soils. While metacid was shown to be retained more than sumithion by clay particles, the oxides (Fe₂O₃ and Al₂O₃) showed a reverse phenomenon. The adsorption is essentially surface phenomenon and shows very little effects of CEC and pH.

A rise in temperature from 10 to 33° resulted in a decrease in adsorption (Table 2). This indicates the exothermic nature of adsorption due to weakening of the attractive forces between the adsorbate molecules and adsorbent surface¹⁶.

The desorption patterns of metacid and sumithion (Figs. 3 and 4) were evaluated from percent desorption values (Table 3). Hysteresis is observed due to irreversible nature of desorption of pesticides. The desorption is inversely related to organic matter content as evident from the following soil order : Burdwan > Purulia > Krishnagar > Kalkdwip > Mohitnagar. Similar results were found in earlier studies¹⁷.

Thermodynamic parameters, viz. ΔG^0 , ΔH^0 and ΔS^0 values, were calculated from the adsorption data²⁶. The ΔG^0 values (Table 4) are small and negative, indicating spontaneity of adsorption. The enthalpy changes (ΔH^0) were small and negative indicating physical nature of adsorption. The values of ΔS^0 is an indication of complex nature of adsorption¹⁸.

Experimental

Soil samples (0–20 cm) were collected from different State Agricultural Farms of West Bengal, located at Burdwan (Inceptisol), Kalkdwip (Entisol), Krishnagar (Inceptisol), Mohitnagar (Entisol) and Purulia (Alfisol). The organic matter and oxides were removed by treatment with hydrogen peroxide and mixture of sodium citrate-bicarbonate-dithionite¹⁹.

TABLE 3—DESORPTION OF ADSORBED METACID AND SUMITHION FROM SOILS

Pesticides	Burdwan soil			Kalkdwip soil			Krishnagar soil			Mohitnagar soil			Purulia soil							
	Adsorption (%)	Desorption (%)		Adsorption (%)	Desorption (%)		Adsorption (%)	Desorption (%)		Adsorption (%)	Desorption (%)		Adsorption (%)	Desorption (%)						
		1st	2nd		3rd	%		1st	2nd		3rd	%		1st	2nd	3rd	%	1st	2nd	3rd
Metacid	30	17	16	14	30	17	16	14	30	17	16	10	40	25	17	16	25	20	19	19
	30	17	16	14	30	17	16	14	30	17	16	10	50	20	13	11	23	22	14	13
	30	22	18	14	33	15	12	13	27	19	18	15	47	18	16	12	23	22	18	13
	27	23	18	14	30	21	16	12	25	20	19	15	45	17	17	14	23	22	18	14
	24	25	22	21	28	22	18	16	24	21	21	16	40	18	17	15	22	23	18	14
	20	29	26	33	27	22	18	17	23	22	23	18	37	18	18	17	20	25	22	21
Sumithion	25	25	30	28	50	15	15	10	37	17	16	10	40	19	15	14	30	31	30	35
	30	21	21	17	53	22	18	15	35	18	16	10	44	21	18	11	40	20	15	11
	36	23	18	18	56	27	28	17	38	17	13	12	46	18	14	10	46	18	17	13
	37	25	22	21	59	21	20	12	40	20	19	12	42	18	16	13	47	20	16	15
	38	26	22	23	58	19	17	10	38	26	22	17	42	19	19	16	48	21	23	21
	41	25	20	21	54	20	18	16	37	27	27	30	44	20	21	17	50	23	27	26

Fig. 3. Retention of metacid by Kakdwip soil : (●) adsorption and (○) desorption.

Mechanical composition, pH (1 : 2.5), electrical conductance (EC_e) of saturation extract, organic matter content, cation-exchange capacity²⁰, free oxides and specific surface area¹⁹ of untreated, organic matter-free and oxide-free soils were determined following standard procedures.

For adsorption experiments, a known amount (1 g) of each adsorbent (soil-untreated, soil-organic matter-free and soil-oxide free) was taken in screw capped centrifuge tubes and shaken for a maximum of 12 h with aqueous solutions (20 ml) of metacid (Metacid 50 EC, produced from Bayer India Ltd., containing 50% methylparathion) and sumithion (Sumithion 50 EC, produced from Rallis India Ltd., containing 50% fenitrothion) in the concentration range 1–50 ppm in a thermostat at 33, 24 and 10° ($\pm 1^\circ$)

respectively. Preliminary kinetic studies confirmed the attainment of equilibrium within 12 h for adsorption of metacid and sumithion by soils. After equilibration, the samples were removed and centrifuged. The supernatant solution (10 ml) of the pesticide was withdrawn and replaced by equal volume of 0.1 N KCl for subsequent desorption experiments (at 33° only) of pesticide from untreated soils. The procedure was repeated in each set for three desorption steps. The supernatants collected for adsorption and desorption experiments were analysed colorimetrically at 555 nm for metacid and sumithion against suitable blank²¹.

Fig. 4. Retention of sumithion by Purulia soil : (●) adsorption and (○) desorption.

TABLE 4—VALUES OF THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS ASSOCIATED WITH ADSORPTION OF METACID AND SUMITHION BY UNTREATED AND TREATED SOILS AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Soil	Treatment	$K_0 \cdot 10^{-2}$						$\Delta G^\circ (\text{KJ mol}^{-1})$						$\Delta H^\circ (\text{kJ mol}^{-1})$		$\Delta S^\circ (\text{JK}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1})$	
		Metacid			Sumithion			Metacid			Sumithion			Metacid	Sumithion	Metacid	Sumithion
		33°	24°	10°	33°	24°	10°	33°	24°	10°	33°	24°	10°	33°	24°	10°	Metacid
Burdawn	Untreated	4.03	6.65	9.92	4.69	6.24	10.47	-15.42	16.21	-16.40	-15.88	16.05	-16.05	-30.37	-25.24	-48.64	-30.91
	O.M.-free	4.63	5.44	6.65	4.93	7.25	10.97	-15.42	-15.67	-15.44	-15.93	-16.46	-16.64	-17.13	-26.44	-5.42	-34.19
	OX-free	9.92	12.12	16.36	19.98	24.40	32.94	-17.73	-17.71	-17.58	-19.53	-19.45	-19.25	-15.97	-15.96	+5.75	+11.67
Kakdwip	Untreated	2.21	3.37	10.96	6.02	8.98	13.39	-13.87	-14.52	-16.64	16.44	-16.97	-17.11	-48.63	-26.44	-11.38	-32.67
	O.M.-free	2.99	3.65	4.59	6.02	8.12	10.97	14.65	-14.72	-14.57	-16.44	-16.71	-16.64	-14.00	-19.84	+2.44	10.96
	OX-free	6.65	9.92	13.92	10.97	16.36	26.97	-16.70	-17.17	-17.11	-17.99	-18.46	18.77	-23.72	29.18	-22.72	36.45
Krishna-gar	Untreated	3.65	9.44	13.39	3.30	4.93	8.15	15.16	-17.08	17.11	14.91	-15.46	-15.59	-46.44	-29.30	101.55	26.87
	O.M.-free	3.30	4.45	8.02	6.65	10.97	16.36	-14.90	-15.21	-15.21	-16.70	-17.46	-17.59	19.86	30.35	16.08	-24.35
	OX-free	8.12	10.96	14.80	10.96	13.39	26.97	-17.22	-17.48	-17.35	17.99	17.96	-18.77	-19.85	26.85	-8.48	39.23
Mohitnagar	Untreated	8.12	13.39	49.15	4.93	10.97	16.36	-17.22	-17.96	-20.20	-15.93	-17.46	-17.59	-54.98	-42.02	123.60	84.63
	O.M.-free	4.46	5.44	6.65	4.46	3.30	6.65	-15.67	-15.21	-15.44	-15.67	-14.46	-15.44	-13.20	7.47	+8.15	+26.16
	OX-free	8.97	10.96	15.33	18.08	22.08	36.40	-17.47	-17.46	-17.43	-19.27	-19.20	-19.49	-16.90	-21.45	1.85	7.26
Purulia	Untreated	3.65	14.80	10.97	3.65	5.44	8.12	-15.16	-18.21	-16.64	-15.16	-15.71	-15.92	-46.14	-26.44	99.83	-36.62
	O.M.-free	6.65	8.98	10.97	5.44	6.65	10.97	-16.70	-16.96	-16.64	-16.18	-16.21	-16.64	-17.13	-21.48	-1.22	-17.35
	OX-free	9.92	10.12	16.36	44.47	54.51	66.34	-17.03	-17.51	-17.58	-21.59	-21.45	-20.91	-15.97	-13.23	+5.75	+27.38

References

- 1 C. A. EDWARDS in "Organic Chemicals in the Soil Environment". eds. C. A. I. GORING and J. W. HAMAKER, Marcel Dekker, New York, 1972, Vol. 2, p. 513.
- 2 G. W. BAILEY and J. L. WHITE, *Residue Rev*, 1970 **29**, 29
- 3 N. SENESI, G. BRUNETTI, P. L. CAVA and T. D. MIANO, *Soil Sci*, 1994, **157**, 176.
- 4 M. BOSETTO, P. ARFAIOLI and P. FUSI, *Soil Sci.*, 1993, **155**, 105.
- 5 M. ADHIKARI and A. K. MANDAL, *J Indian Chem Soc*, 1993, **70**, 223.
- 6 D. A. LAIRD, E. BARRIUSO, R. H. DOWDY and W. C. KOSKINEN *Soil Sci Soc Am J*, 1992, **56**, 62.
- 7 G. D. CANCELA, E. R. TABOADA and F. SANCHEZ-RASERO, *J Soil Sci*, 1992 **43**, 99.
- 8 M. ADHIKARI, A. K. MANDAL and RAY, *J Indian Soc. Soil Sci.*, 1991, **39**, 680
- 9 M. ADHIKARI, A. K. MANDAL, A. RAY and N. DAS, *Clay Res.*, 1991 **10**, 52
- 10 C. H. GILES, T. H. MCEWAN, S. N. NAKHWA and D. SMITH, *J Chem Soc.*, 1960, 3973
- 11 M. J. SANCHEZ-MARTIN and M. SANCHEZ-CAMAZANO, *Soil Sci* 1991, **152**, 283.
- 12 A. FELSOT and P. A. DAHM, *J Agric Food Chem*, 1979 **27**, 557
- 13 J. B. WEBER and L. R. SWAIN, *Soil Sci*, 1993, **156**, 171
- 14 R. M. JOHNSON and J. T. SIMA, *Soil Sci.*, 1993, **155**, 139
- 15 G. W. SNEDECOR and W. G. COCHRAN, "Statistical Methods Oxford and IBH, New Delhi, 1967
- 16 R. VAN BLADEL and A. MOREALE, *Soil Sci Soc Am Proc* 1974 **38**, 244.
- 17 D. E. PECK, D. L. CORWIN and W. J. FARMER, *J Environ Qual* 1980, **9**, 101.
- 18 J. W. BIGGAR and M. W. CHEUNG, *Soil Sci Soc Am Proc*, 1973 **37**, 863.
- 19 C. A. BLACK in "Methods of Soil Analysis" ed. C. A. BLACK, Am Soc. Agron., Madison, 1965, Vol. 2
- 20 M. L. JACKSON, "Soil Chemical Analysis", Prentice-Hall of India New Delhi, 1973.
- 21 G. ZWEIG in "Analytical Methods for Pesticides, Plant Growth Regulators and Food Additives", ed. G. ZWEIG, Academic New York, 1964, Vol. II.